

PROMOTION OF ONLINE TEACHING THROUGH INTERACTIVE LESSONS

Amonova Gulnora Zarifovna

Telephone number +998996602854, amonovag58@gmail.com

Teacher of School number № 44

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12635625>

Annotation: The effective ways of interactive lessons which are useful for online teaching are illustrated in this research paper.

Keywords: Kahoot, googleclassroom, incorporating videos, animations, materials, Student-centered approaches, project-based learning, peer teaching

Introduction

Interactive lessons are educational sessions designed to actively engage students in the learning process through participation and interaction. Unlike traditional lecture-based teaching, interactive lessons focus on student involvement and often use technology to enhance engagement and facilitate active learning. We have been living in a digital age especially for this reason we should change the ways of teaching. In a pandemic period more and more educators and learners obliged to utilize the internet and the benefits of online lessons went up. In this thesis several beneficial keys are illustrated.

Main part

Promoting online teaching through interactive lessons involves several strategies to engage students and enhance learning outcomes. Here are some key aspects:

1. Use of Technology

- Interactive Platforms: Utilize platforms like Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Google Classroom, or specialized educational tools like Nearpod, Kahoot!, and Edupuzzle. By these platforms teachers can use the foreign songs or videos to support interactive lessons¹. All these platforms serve to save the time of both teachers and students effectively. These tools of technology can not only be used in the unusual lessons but they also used in the traditional lessons so as to attract the pupils or the students' attention. As a example, some games may be organized on the Zoom. For instance, by the uncomplete pictures in ppt students may say divesre opinions together on the online. In this case teachers should only turn on the demonstration of Zoom platform.

2. Engagement Techniques

¹ Xolmuratov, J. (2023). THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSON. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(6), 1203-1205.

- Live Polls and Quizzes: Tools like Mentimeter or Poll Everywhere can be used during lessons to keep students engaged and assess understanding in real-time. In this method pupils pass survey by not knowing their peers or their classmates.² Live polls is more useful for the topic “what is your favorite friend” which was posed in the curriculum of Public education. By the result of polls or quizzes the teachers can plan their future online lessons according to the tastes, wishes, levels and conditions of the pupils³. Owing to difficult to write in the online lessons such kind of polls or quizzes can facilitate to conduct the lessons.

- Breakout Rooms: Divide students into smaller groups for discussions and collaborative work.

- Gamification: Integrate game-like elements such as points, badges, and leaderboards to motivate students.

3. Content Design

- Interactive Videos: Use platforms like Edu puzzle to add questions, notes, and voiceovers to videos.

- Virtual Labs and Simulations: Tools like PhET Interactive Simulations or Labster provide hands-on experience in a virtual environment.

- Adaptive Learning: Use systems that adapt the content and difficulty based on the student's performance.

4. Student-Centered Approaches

- Flipped Classroom: Provide pre-recorded lectures for students to watch at their own pace, then use live sessions for discussion and problem-solving.

- Project-Based Learning: Encourage students to work on projects that require applying what they've learned in practical scenarios.

- Peer Teaching: Allow students to teach each other, reinforcing their knowledge and building communication skills.

5. Professional Development

- Training for Educators: Offer training sessions on using digital tools and designing interactive lessons.

- Community Building: Create online communities for educators to share resources, experiences, and best practices.

6. Feedback and Assessment

² Muir, T., Wang, I., Trimble, A., Mainsbridge, C., & Douglas, T. (2022). Using interactive online pedagogical approaches to promote student engagement. *Education Sciences*, 12(6), 415.

³ Palaigeorgiou, G., & Papadopoulou, A. (2019). Promoting self-paced learning in the elementary classroom with interactive video, an online course platform and tablets. *Education and Information Technologies*, 24, 805-823.

- Formative Assessments: Regularly use formative assessments to gauge student understanding and adjust teaching strategies accordingly.
- Interactive Assignments: Use tools like Google Forms, Quizlet, or Padlet for assignments that encourage interaction and creativity.
- Student Feedback: Regularly collect feedback from students to improve the teaching process.

Conclusion

By integrating these elements, educators can create a dynamic and engaging online teaching environment that promotes active learning and student participation. The different styles of learning and needs can be adapted in the lessons interactive.

Interactive lessons transform the traditional classroom dynamic by making learning a more active, engaging, and personalized experience. By incorporating game-like elements, real-world applications, and interactive content, these lessons aim to keep students motivated and engaged throughout the learning process.

References:

1. "Teaching Online: A Practical Guide" by Susan Ko and Steve Rossen
2. "The Online Teaching Survival Guide" by Judith V. Boettcher and Rita-Marie Conrad
3. "e-Learning and the Science of Instruction: Proven Guidelines for Consumers and Designers of Multimedia Learning" by Ruth C. Clark and Richard E. Mayer
4. Muir, T., Wang, I., Trimble, A., Mainsbridge, C., & Douglas, T. (2022). Using interactive online pedagogical approaches to promote student engagement. *Education Sciences*, 12(6), 415.
5. Palaigeorgiou, G., & Papadopoulou, A. (2019). Promoting self-paced learning in the elementary classroom with interactive video, an online course platform and tablets. *Education and Information Technologies*, 24, 805-823.
6. Xolmuratov, J. (2023). THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSON. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(6), 1203-1205.
7. Xolbayev, X. (2022). DIFFERENCES AND ADVANTAGES OF NEW METHODS TO SPEAK THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 1(7), 96-101.